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Solid Oxide Cell Technology for Space Applications

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Abstract

The solid oxide cell (SOC) technology offers many possibilities for space applications, such as power generation, energy storage, oxygen and hydrogen pumping or purification and electrolysis. The European Space Agency (ESA) is very interested and active in developing this technology for future space missions.

One of the most promising applications appears to be an energy storage system for application on Mars based on a reversible solid oxide fuel cell. The advantage of this system would be that it could allow for in situ resource utilisation (ISRU) of the CO₂ atmosphere of Mars. Thus, the reactant would not have to be taken from Earth, which reduces drastically the launch mass of a potential mission. Energy is stored in the form of CO and O₂ coming from the preceding electrolysis of CO₂. When electric energy is needed, these two reactants are electrochemically recombined.

Another potential application for the SOC technology is the electrolysis of water coming from local resources on the moon for provision of breathable O₂ for astronauts and H₂ as rocket fuel.

This paper aims at giving an insight of the possible applications in space, the benefits and challenges, and which developments have been, are currently and will be carried out by ESA and its partners.

Introduction

In the past, fuel cell technology has been successfully applied in American manned spaceflight programmes like Gemini (early proton exchange membrane (PEM)), Apollo (alkaline) and the Space Shuttle (alkaline). These were all primary fuel cell technologies and could not be recharged. To generate electric power, H₂ and O₂ were consumed by a fuel cell. The product water could be consumed by the astronauts.

At ESA, fuel cells were previously considered for application predominantly in very high power telecom spacecraft [1]. In this application, the reactants have to be kept in a closed loop. The product water is collected and electrolysed when electric power is available. The H₂ and O₂ are stored and consumed by a fuel cell whenever electric power is needed. This kind of fuel cell system is referred to as a regenerative fuel cell system (RFCS). RFCS have a potential for high specific energy as compared to secondary batteries. However, the achievable specific energy greatly depends on the size of the system and increases with the amount of energy stored as can be seen in Figure 1. For Li-Ion batteries the specific energy does not change with system size.

In Figure 1, the achievable specific energy is compared for Li-Ion (150 Wh/kg), primary fuel cell system (FCS) and RFCS. Regenerative fuel cell systems (RFCS) could outperform batteries in terms of specific energy for large amounts of stored energy (Technical Note 2 of [2]). However, the increased energy density comes at a price: Compared to Li-Ion batteries, for which the roundtrip energy-efficiency of charge/discharge is above 90%, for RFCS it can be expected that it will be much lower in the range of 50%, which has implications on the system design especially on the sizing of solar generators commonly used for space missions.

Figure 1 Evolution of energy density with stored amount of energy [2]

Several ESA-initiated activities have been completed in the domain [3-6], all of which were based on PEM technology. The concept of RFCS was successfully demonstrated with the required lifetime [7, 8]. Achieving the required specific energy, the thermal aspects and the reliability of the envisaged RFCS are considered to be key technical hurdles [6]. Nevertheless, in the ESA ARTES program the development of an RFCS for large telecom satellites is continued [9]. The developed systems can be easily adapted to the promising concept of high altitude pseudo satellites (HAPS). In HAPS the availability of very high specific energy density (>350 Wh/kg) technology is mission enabling. HAPS keep their position at around 20 km altitude requiring a rather high power. During the day they rely on power supplied by solar generators and at night by power coming from an energy storage

system based on batteries or RFCS. The technologies developed for telecom satellites or HAPS (Figure 2) can also be applied for lunar exploration, e.g. for the lunar night survival without radioisotope technologies. During the lunar night, which is extremely cold (~90 K) and lasts around 14 days, spacecraft or probes need to have sufficient power and energy to maintain an acceptable temperature in sensitive elements.

Figure 2 Neosat (left) an example of high power telecom satellite. HAPS (right)

There are different potential applications for fuel cells in space including primary fuel cells, electrolyser systems and regenerative fuel cell systems.

1. High power telecom spacecraft
2. Large telecommunication satellites and HAPS
3. Lunar night survival
4. For Mars robotic and human exploration with SOC technology using CO₂ as local resource
5. Missions to Neptune/Uranus using liquid CH₄/O₂ primary fuel cell for power provision from Jupiter distance onwards. Within the distance Earth to Jupiter, solar power can be used.
6. On Lunar or Martian manned stations
7. “Water propulsion”: Generation of H₂/O₂ rocket fuel coming from electrolysis of H₂O
8. Oxygen provision for manned missions using local H₂O resources on the Moon and on Mars
9. Functional power on launchers
10. Biomass-based fuel cell for manned space exploration

At the present time, HAPS and lunar night survival are seen to be the most promising applications. HAPS developments may currently not be funded by any ESA program, but since developments for high power telecom spacecraft are ongoing, the developed technologies can easily be applied for HAPS by the industrial partner.

Concerning human exploration to the Moon and to Mars, there is a lot of momentum with the recent American push to return to the Moon. In the Global Exploration Roadmap [10], published by a consortium of international space agencies, the next steps of a human settlement on the moon and a further step to be taken towards Mars are described. Fuel cell technologies are highly advantageous, if not mission enabling, for some of the envisaged missions. European fuel cell technologies should be at the forefront so that they can be applied in potential missions in the coming decade.

Because of the higher technology readiness level (TRL), the baseline technology for RFCS for telecom satellites, lunar night survival and water propulsion was mostly based on the PEM technology, but it could also be based on SOC.

For energy storage on Mars, SOC energy storage systems are very promising because they allow to utilise the CO₂ in the Martian atmosphere. Consequently, the reactant would not have to be brought from Earth. Maximising the specific energy (in terms of Wh/kg), reliability and thermal aspects are the main drivers for space fuel cell systems.

Current solid oxide fuel cell and electrolyser technologies are at relatively low TRL in Europe for space applications. There are several significant technical barriers that need to be overcome in order to apply fuel cells in future space missions:

1. The resilience of fuel cells stacks to the mechanical environment during launch
2. The stack mass for terrestrial stationary applications is much too high for space applications (up to 0.1 kW/kg versus 1 kW/kg needed for space). Stack design to reach mass targets is challenging
3. System complexity, reliability, and redundancy approach
4. System integration and balancing of plant optimisation
5. Thermal management in space
6. Operation in zero gravity (spin in of terrestrial applications).
7. Development of gas storage tanks
8. Development of space grade components (like valves, pressure regulators, pumps)
9. Operation with pure oxygen instead of air

Mars applications

Energy storage

The Martian atmosphere offers up to 15 mbar of CO₂, which can be utilised as an SOC based energy storage system for long duration energy provision. Energy can be stored in the form of CO and O₂ coming from the preceding electrolysis of CO₂. As compared to PEM, for which CO₂ is a catalyst poison, SOC can utilise the CO₂ as reactant. When electric energy is needed, these two reactants are electrochemically recombined. These systems have been studied already in ESA led activities [11-13] and the results have been published in the proceedings of the European Space Power Conference [14-16].

Such provisions are very relevant to the exploration of Mars. In particular to operations on its surface during nighttime, but also during periods of reduced sunlight availability e.g. during dust storms that can last for weeks if not months. The envisaged energy storage system comprises a CO₂ compressor (pumping system), an SOC stack/electrolyser (the unit that does both electrolysis and electric power generation), thermal control and gas bladders for the storage of CO, O₂, and CO₂. The stored energy capability of the system can be selected independently from the stack power (unlike with with batteries) by the size of the CO and O₂ bladders. In [13], a first designing and testing of a breadboard model based on reversible Solid Oxide Fuel Cells were performed. At the end of the test campaign, some issues were found with uncontrolled carbon formation, which did not allow for long duration operation. The main problem was identified to be insufficient temperature in certain regions of the stack. This favoured the formation of carbon by the Boudouard reaction and catalyzed by the nickel-electrode. To avoid this situation, ESA partners have developed carbon-tolerant perovskitic-type oxide materials La_{0.75}Sr_{0.25}Cr_{0.9}Fe_{0.1}O_{3-δ} (LSCrF), which are Ni-free and therefore do not contribute to carbon formation [17]. The avoidance of carbon formation is one of the major challenges for this technology. Another challenge will be the operation on pure oxygen instead of air.

In a currently running ESA activity [18], the performance of a redesigned breadboard system taking into account the lessons learned from the previous one shall be demonstrated without carbon formation. In a follow-on activity the development to an engineering model is planned. The target in this activity for the complete system is to build a breadboard at TRL 5.

Oxygen production from CO₂

Any manned exploration surface mission will rely on the availability of breathable oxygen for the crew. As already discussed, the SOC technology is well suited to convert CO₂ to CO and O₂. It is about to be utilised for the first time on Mars for oxygen production demonstration. On NASA's Mars 2020 *Perseverance* rover, an in-situ resource utilisation (ISRU) experiment (named *Moxie*), is embarked to demonstrate the feasibility of O₂ production from the Martian CO₂ [19]. The rover is currently on the way and is expected to land in February 2021.

Oxygen production from H₂O

On Mars, the presence of H₂O was confirmed [20, 21]. In higher latitudes even very pure water ice can be found. On the more accessible latitudes close to the equator ice containing soil may be available. The predominant water resource is present as hydrated minerals. Further to this, on Martian missions there is a possibility to manufacture H₂/O₂ from water that is created in-situ by the carbo-thermal reduction of regolith by methane [22]. Another important point in the context of providing oxygen to manned surface missions is that the gas-mixture used in the crew cabin is lost through leakage and through air-lock operation. The oxygen can be replenished using the electrolysis of water coming from ISRU. However, the inert nitrogen, used to dilute the oxygen to a similar concentration as on Earth is lost and there is no easy way of providing this essential gas to the life support system. In [23] this point is addressed. The Martian atmosphere contains around 2.7% of N₂ and 1.6% of Ar, which could be used to create breathable air. This is a very important issue.

Chemicals production from H₂O and CO₂

SOC technology is also particularly suitable for producing syngas when CO₂ and H₂O are co-electrolysed. On Mars CO₂ is available independent of the location and water can be found in certain places, in which a co-electrolysis plant for production of chemicals could be feasible. Syngas can be converted using different catalysts to products which are of use for future space missions (e.g. methanol, methane or synthetic diesel).

Lunar applications

Energy Storage

For future missions to the lunar surface a capability for lunar night survival will be needed. One example of such a mission is the European Large Logistic Lander (EL3), of which an impression is shown in Figure 3. EL3 will have the capability to bring food, water, air and equipment to the surface, in support of crewed exploration projects such as NASA's Artemis programme. It is foreseen that EL3 will require the capability to survive on the surface through the lunar night. The most high-performing and reliable way to achieve this would be to rely on radioisotope technologies, e.g. radioisotope heating units (RHU) or radioisotope thermoelectric generators (RTG). As an alternative to these technologies, RFCS are currently being developed in an ESA-led R&D activity [2]. The development is based on PEM technology because of the higher TRL, but in principle SOC technology could also be

used for this application. RFCS become even more attractive when the emitted thermal power can be utilised in addition to the electrical output.

Figure 3 European Large Logistic Lander unloading cargo

Oxygen production from H₂O

It has been confirmed in the past years that H₂O is present at the lunar poles but it is not yet fully clear in which configuration this water is available [24, 25]. There are many unknowns concerning this point but it can be assumed that pre-processed water taken from this water ice bearing consolidated regolith could be fed to an electrolyser system based on SOEC technology. As for Martian missions, also on the Moon there is a possibility to manufacture H₂/O₂ from water that is created in-situ by the carbo-thermal reduction of regolith by methane [22].

The solid oxide electrolyser cell (SOEC) technology offers many advantages compared to PEM such as higher efficiency, faster electrode kinetics due to the high operating temperature and higher tolerance for impurities. Because of several advantages the SOEC technology has over PEM, an activity based on SOEC was launched for assessing a system that can convert in-situ H₂O on the Lunar or Martian surface to H₂ and O₂ [26]. SOEC technology was also chosen for assessment in order to avoid duplicating the parallel ongoing research on PEM. The objectives of the activity are to specify, design, build and test a breadboard of a high-pressure electrolyser based on the SOEC technology, which is capable of creating hydrogen and oxygen from ISRU water in the Lunar and Martian environment. The aim is to demonstrate the feasibility of high pressure SOE technology (up to 10 bars) for exploration surface missions.

A concept of the HP-SOE system is shown in Figure 4. The ISRU material is injected into the system, is pre-processed to extract the water. The processing itself is not part of the bread boarding. The dried material from which the water is extracted is released and is no longer useful (except the stored heat). Then this water is converted to gaseous water in a steamer and subsequently enters the SOE stack. At the anode the water is converted to H₂ and O²⁻ ions. The latter migrate through the SOEC material to the cathode side. The released electrons are conducted via the external electric circuit to the cathode side. At the cathode side the two O²⁻ ions are recombined with electrons to form O₂.

The formed H₂ and O₂ are collected in gas storage tanks. The unreacted water in the H₂ gas stream has to be separated and fed again to the electrolyser stack. The stack is equipped with an electric heater to reach the operating temperature of the SOEC electrolyte material (> 500° C). In order to reach a high system efficiency, the thermal management system (dotted line) is of utmost importance. Further components will be needed for the breadboard of this activity, which are not shown in Figure 4, e.g. gas valves, pressure regulators, safety valves, flow meters and pressure gauges.

This system will only be able to supply O₂. On the moon there is no access to an “inert” gas to allow for mixing of air and it seems likely that N₂ will have to be brought from Earth.

Electrochemical pumping

The possibility to conduct oxygen ions through a solid state material at elevated temperatures can be seen as a gift from nature. ESA is currently looking into the possibilities for electrochemical pumping of O₂, which can be used for pumping without moving parts as for example in mechanical pumps. Pumps need regular maintenance and are prone to failure, which is why for space missions the use of pumps is generally minimised. With electrochemical pumps gaseous oxygen can be compressed to higher pressure level by the use of electrical energy. Furthermore, the O₂ purity is expected to be higher when electrochemical systems are used.

Figure 4 Draft concept of the HP-SOEC system that is to be developed in [26]

Electrochemical pumping can also be used for separating oxygen from other gases or for purifying purposes. ESA is planning to issue an invitation to tender (ITT) in the coming months, in which the requirements and the statement of work will be defined. The objective of the activity will be to develop electrochemical O₂ pumping technologies and to demonstrate the performance at TRL 3.

Electrochemical pumping of H₂ using SOEC technology is also seen as a very promising technology for space applications but it has to compete with PEM technology, which is already highly advanced. This option has currently not been studied yet for space applications by ESA.

Electrochemical O₂ pumping has been demonstrated in 2007 by Spirin et al [27]. In 2016 researchers at NASA's Glenn Research center have built electrochemical O₂ compressors for space applications. The TRL is not known and no information on the pressure level could be found.

Chemicals production

As already mentioned, the SOC technology is capable of converting dry CO₂ to CO and O₂. If the conditions are well controlled carbon formation by the Boudouard equilibrium can be avoided. The process allows to split the very stable CO₂ molecule and bring it to a more activated state for subsequent reactions. Similarly H₂O can also be electrolysed in an SOC electrolyser. If both CO₂ and H₂O electrolysis is combined at the fuel side of the reactor CO/H₂ (syngas) is formed, which can be used in a downstream extra reactor to produce different chemicals, which will be of use for future manned mission to Mars. Methane, methanol or synthetic fuels are some examples of the products that could be made on the Martian surface using in situ water from the ground and CO₂ from the atmosphere.

Water Propulsion System

Water propulsion is an innovative propulsion technology where water is split in orbit over a longer period with low electric power into hydrogen and oxygen at high pressures. These gases are stored and burned when a thrust is needed (e.g. for deorbiting a satellite at the end of mission). In the frame of an ESA R&D activity [28] different aspects of this technology were investigated. The activity is based on PEM technology but theoretically the SOEC technology could also be applied with the potential advantage of reaching a higher power and efficiency as compared to the PEM technology.

ESA Roadmap

The process of harmonising and elaborating a future strategy for the electrochemical energy storage has been completed in 2019 [29]. As well as batteries and supercapacitors, also fuel cells are included. The most recent roadmap agreed with industry and ESA member state delegations is shown in Figure 5. As mentioned in the electrochemical energy storage dossier, the current fuel cell and electrolyser technology is at a relatively low TRL in Europe for space applications. Most of the activities are on fuel cells in general not prescribing a technology. An evaluation of solid oxide cell based RFCS system for HAPS is foreseen as well as the already mentioned electrochemical pumping.

The roadmap activities are subject to constant revision and reconsideration and if an activity is not foreseen in it, it is still possible to launch an activity that is deemed important.

Similar to batteries there is a market focus on the larger terrestrial industry and it can be a challenge to focus commercial organisation on the relatively small volume applications in space, especially given the long-term application horizon on exploration fuel cell usage. Because of this, the progress through the TRL spectrum is slow and the relative cost projection for new systems can be prohibitive. Space fuel cells can bring benefits for terrestrial R&D and vice-versa. It must be ensured that the developments will bring benefits to both sector of activities.

Summary and Conclusion

This paper has given an overview of the past, current and future ESA activities in the domain of fuel cells, electrolysers and regenerative fuel cell systems. ESA has been active in the field of space fuel cells in the past decades. An increased interest for fuel cell systems in space applications can be noticed. It appears that different companies are interested to assess their fuel cell, electrolyser and balance of plant components for space applications. The endorsement of the harmonisation dossier [29] in the field of fuel cells by industry and delegations also confirms the increasing interest in these technologies. More than 16 fuel cell related activities with a planned budget of above 12 million Euros have been endorsed in the harmonisation dossier of electrochemical energy storage in 2019.

A point of utmost importance is the spin-in from terrestrial technologies for space applications, taking into account the space requirements like high performance, reliability, mechanical resilience, radiation, vacuum, thermal management and lifetime.

Figure 5 The fuel cell activities as agreed during the European Space Technology Harmonisation process in 2019

Many of the current terrestrial developments in SOC technology like dry electrolysis, water electrolysis, co-electrolysis, reversible SOCs that have gained momentum in the past years. The vision that is being followed is that a diverse set of companies and organisations from ESA member states contribute to future space endeavors that will rely on fuel cell/electrolyser technologies.

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